

STUDIES IN THE PYRIDINE SERIES. PART I. AN ATTEMPT TO SYNTHESISE 2-METHYL-4-ETHYLPYRIDINE.

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2 : 6-Dimethyl-4-ethyl-1 : 4 dihydropyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate has been obtained by condensing ethyl acetoacetate, propionaldehyde, ammonia in presence of piperidine. The dihydro ester, on oxidation in ether solution with nitrous fumes or by iodine in alcohol solution, gives 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate. The potassium salt obtained by hydrolysis when distilled with soda lime gives 2 : 6 dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine described by Engelmann. 2 : 6 Dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine has been condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of zinc chloride, when 2 : 6-distyryl-4 ethylpyridine, 2-styryl-4-ethyl-6-methylpyridine and α phenyl- β -6-(2-methyl-4-ethyl)-pyridyl-ethanol are formed. The monostyryl derivative gives a picrate, m.p. 232-33° but is formed in too small a quantity for detailed examination.

It has been mentioned (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 399), that one of the basic products isolated by alkaline degradation of strychnine and brucine appeared to be 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine from its physical constants. An attempt has been made to synthesise it by Hantzsch's general method for pyridines (*Annalen*, 1882, **215**, 1; *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 1946; 1885, **18**, 1744-2579). Engelmann (*Annalen*, 1885, **231**, 44) obtained ethyl dihydroparvolinedicarboxylate by condensing a mixture of ethyl acetoacetate, propionaldehyde and alcoholic ammonia which on oxidation with nitrous acid gave ethylparvoline. It was hoped that it would give a monobenzylidine derivative with benzaldehyde, whence by oxidation and subsequent decarboxylation 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine would be obtained.

2 : 6-Dimethyl-4-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydropyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate, prepared by a modified method (*vide* experimental) has m.p. 110° and gives 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate on oxidation with iodine or nitrous acid in better yield in ether solution. The crude potassium salt obtained by hydrolysis with alcoholic potassium hydroxide has been mixed with soda lime and distilled. From the distillate 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine has been obtained and when it is condensed with benzaldehyde in a sealed tube first at 140° and then at 180-85° in presence of zinc chloride, it gives the best yield of monostyryl product along with a distyryl derivative and a third substance, which from the analytical data, appears to be an aldol condensation product of the base and benzaldehyde. All the three products are formed irrespective of the proportions in which the reactants are present, but excess of benzaldehyde favours the formation of the distyryl product. The separation of the three products is effected by

taking advantage of the solubility of their salts. The monoethyl compound is not sufficient for further purification, detailed examination and characterisation. Further work is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2 : 6-Dimethyl-4-ethyl-1 : 4-dihydropyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate.—To a mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (115 g., 2 mol.) and propionaldehyde (25 g., 1 mol.) cooled in a freezing mixture was added cooled piperidine (16 g.). The mixture was kept in the freezing mixture for 2 hours and then allowed to stand overnight at 0°. Ammonia (a little more than 1 mol., 8 g.) was passed into the mixture and after the addition of a little more ammonia solution (*d* 0.880, 5 c.c.) was heated in a closed flask at 100° for 4 hours. After cooling the light yellow coloured mixture was decomposed with water when the dihydro ester separated in bright yellow flocks. It was well washed with hot water (yield 115 g., 89%). After crystallisation from ethanol in pale yellow prisms it had m.p. 112° (corr.) (*cf.* Engelmann, *loc. cit.*). The substance is soluble in ether, acetone, chloroform, ethyl acetate, benzene and alcohol but difficultly soluble in petroleum ether and insoluble in water. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo* : C, 64.1 ; H, 8.1 ; N, 5.1. $C_{15}H_{23}O_4N$ requires C, 64.1 ; H, 8.2 ; N, 5.0 per cent).

The oxidation of the foregoing dihydro-ester with nitrous acid was best conducted in ether solution by passing nitrous fumes. After the removal of ether (washing of the ether solution with water to remove excess of nitrous acid was found undesirable) the residue was made alkaline with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether. After the removal of the solvent the residue was extracted with petroleum ether in which the original dihydro-ester was insoluble. The unchanged ester was resubmitted to oxidation. The petroleum ether solution was washed with water, dried over potassium hydroxide and allowed to stand overnight at 0° to remove traces of the dihydro-ester. The solvent was removed and the base distilled at 135-40°/0.5 mm. (pale yellow liquid).

The oxidation in ether solution gave much better yield than in alcohol. Oxidation was also tried with iodine in alcoholic solution. Dihydro-ester (4 g., 1 mol.) was added to a solution of iodine (3.6 g., 1 mol.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) and the solution was refluxed on the steam-bath for 1 hour. The solution was concentrated to 5 c.c. and after making alkaline with sodium carbonate was extracted with ether and the excess of iodine was removed by sulphur dioxide. The ester was isolated as hydrochloride whence the base was liberated with alkali and extracted with ether. The residue from ether was dissolved in petroleum ether when unchanged product (0.4 g.)

remained undissolved. The residue from petroleum ether was distilled at $135-140^{\circ}/0.5$ mm.

The *picrate* of 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate was prepared from an ethereal solution of the base and picric acid in acetone when it separated as a mass of long lemon-yellow needles. After washing with water it was recrystallised from alcohol or water as hexagonal prisms, m.p. 116° . It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform and water, insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. It lost 3.4% H_2O at 100° (calc. for 1 H_2O , 3.4 per cent). [Found in material after drying at 100° in *vacuo* : C, 49.8 ; H, 5.0 ; N, 11.2. $C_{15}H_{21}O_4N \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 49.6 ; H, 4.7 ; N, 11.0 per cent).

The dihydro-ester was hydrolysed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and the crude potassium salt (1 part) obtained by evaporation was mixed with soda lime (2 parts) and distilled in a tube sealed at one end. The base distilled at $184-86^{\circ}$ to a straw-coloured fuming liquid with a strong odour, yield 90% (b.p. 186° , cf. Engelmann). The *picrate* of the base was obtained as bright yellow prisms and after recrystallisation from alcohol had m.p. 121° (Engelmann gives $119-120^{\circ}$). [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo* : C, 49.5 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 15.0. $C_9H_{13}N \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 49.5 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 15.4 per cent]. The *hydrochloride*, prepared by precipitation with hydrogen chloride of the ethereal solution of the base, was hygroscopic, pinkish long needles, m.p. 97° . It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, and water.

Condensation of 2 : 6-Dimethyl-4-ethylpyridine with Benzaldehyde.—A mixture of the base (7 g., 1 mol.), benzaldehyde (6.5 g., 1.2 mol.) and zinc chloride (1 g.) showing a green fluorescence was heated in a sealed tube first at 140° for 4 hours and then at $180-85^{\circ}$ for 4 hours more. The resulting thick reddish liquid was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried over potassium hydroxide. The residue from ether after being distilled in steam to remove benzaldehyde and unreacted base, was taken up in petroleum ether ($40-60^{\circ}$). The solution after standing for some hours was filtered from a slight sediment and hydrogen chloride was led into the solution, when a sticky precipitate of the hydrochloride separated. It was dissolved in a little methanol and the solution precipitated by ether. The process was repeated two times and the filtrate combined, a small quantity of tarry matter being neglected. The clear solution showed a greenish blue fluorescence and on keeping at 0° deposited a light yellow crystalline mass of hydrochloride "A" (0.4 g.). The filtrate, on adding picric acid in acetone solution, gave bright yellow prisms, (*picrate* "B") a further yield of which was obtained by concentrating the solution (5 g.). The solids were

washed with hot acetone to remove any picrate of "A" which might have been present. Finally, the mother-liquor from the picrate was evaporated to dryness. The residue was triturated with sodium hydroxide solution. The resulting clear solution after the addition of water was then extracted with ether. The ether extract, after washing with water and drying over potassium carbonate, was treated with hydrogen chloride when an insoluble hydrochloride was precipitated. This was filtered and washed with ether. It was recrystallised by adding ether till turbidity to its methyl alcoholic solution and keeping at 0° when it separated in large white cubes (hydrochloride "C").

These experiments were conducted under varying conditions but in every case all the above three products were obtained as shown in the table below, even when only one molecule of benzaldehyde to one molecule of the base was used.

TABLE I.

Reactants.	Temp.	HCl of "A".	Picrate of "B".	HCl of "C".	Picrate of unreacted base.
(a) 1 Mol. base, 3 mol. benzaldehyde in an atmosphere of nitrogen	140°	0.6 g.	1 g.	2 g.	2 g.
(b) 1 Mol. base, 1 mol. benzaldehyde in a sealed tube.	140°	0.2	1	2.5	2.5
(c) 1 Mol. base, 1 mol. benzaldehyde in a sealed tube.	180-190°	0.6	2.5	2	1.5
(d) 1 Mol. base, 1.2 mol. benzaldehyde in a sealed tube.	140° and then 180-185°	0.4	5	2	0.5

Fraction A.—2:6-Distyryl-4-ethylpyridine Hydrochloride.—The hydrochloride "A" on recrystallisation from methanol had m. p. 271-72° (decomp.). In chloroform and alcohol solution it showed a blue fluorescence. [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 78.9; H, 6.4; N, 4.4; Cl, 10.0. $C_{23}H_{21}N$, HCl requires C, 79.4; H, 6.3; N, 4.0; Cl, 10.2 per cent].

2:6-Distyryl-4-ethylpyridine Chloroplatinate.—The chloroplatinate was obtained in serrated prisms by adding an aqueous solution of platinum chloride to a solution of the hydrochloride in alcohol. It is insoluble in alcohol and water, m.p. 263° (decomp.). [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 53.7; H, 4.3; Pt, 18.4. $(C_{23}H_{21}N, HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires C, 53.5; H, 4.3; Pt, 18.9 per cent].

The *aurichloride*, prepared in methanol solution with aqueous gold chloride, was obtained in golden yellow glistening plates. It is easily

soluble in chloroform, acetone and hot alcohol and insoluble in water, m. p. 200°.

α-Phenyl-β-6-(2-methyl-4-ethyl)-pyridyl-ethanol.—The base as obtained before converting it into the hydrochloride "C" was a thick syrupy brownish liquid. It is soluble in all the organic solvents and so far has not been obtained crystalline.

Fraction C.—α-Phenyl-β-6-(2-methyl-4-ethyl)-pyridyl-ethanol Hydrochloride.—The hydrochloride was obtained as above and on recrystallisation from alcohol-ether mixture it separated in perfectly white cubes. It is soluble in alcohol, chloroform, hot acetone and water, m. p. 175°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 68·8, 68·9; H, 7·0, 6·9; Cl, 12·6. $C_{16}H_{19}ON, HCl$ requires C, 69·2; H, 7·2; Cl, 12·7 per cent).

The *chloroplatinate*, prepared by adding an aqueous solution of platinum chloride to a methyl alcohol solution of the hydrochloride and diluting till turbidity and then keeping at 0° for a week, separated as an amorphous mass. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform and water. It softens at 85° and gradually melts at 125°. The *picrate*, which came down as oily drops when an aqueous solution of picric acid was added to a methyl alcoholic solution of the hydrochloride, became crystalline on adding water to the solution and on scratching and standing it separated in prisms. It is easily soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, benzene and very sparingly in ether. It lost nothing on drying at 100°. [Found in dried material: C, 56·6; H, 4·5; N, 12·3. $C_{16}H_{19}ON \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 56·2; H, 4·7; N, 11·9 per cent].

Fraction B.—After purification as picrate it analysed for the picrate of monostyryl derivative. The quantity was not sufficient for further characterisation. The picrate had m. p. 232-33°. [Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 59·2; H, 4·8; N, 12·1. $C_{16}H_{17}N, C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 58·4; H, 4·4; N, 12·4 per cent].

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